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**Title: Plant health case study developed to accompany the
EA-4/18 guidance document**

Validation of diagnostic tests to support plant health

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Abstract:

The 5th work package of the VALITEST project aimed at developing guidelines on a horizontal approach allowing the laboratories to undertake proficiency testing (PT) without having to participate in proficiency tests for all the tests they use.

As a follow-up to the work carried out within this work-package, a case study has been developed to accompany the EA-4/18 guidance document. It aims at facilitating the implementation of the approach presented in the EA guidance document by laboratories working in the field of plant health.

Partners involved: ANSES, EPPO, NVWA
Task 5.3

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Background

In 2010, the European co-operation for Accreditation (EA) approved an advisory document EA-4/18 INF:2010 Guidance on the level and frequency of proficiency testing participation. It recognizes that participating in a specific proficiency testing (PT) for every test* is unlikely to be feasible. It suggests to laboratories that they identify sets of tests for which the outcome of a PT using one test can be directly correlated to their proficiency in the use of other tests. This approach limits the number of PTs a laboratory should participate in (although not as significantly as a fully horizontal approach), and the efforts of the laboratory, while ensuring the validity of the results. This document also includes case studies for different disciplines. EA recommends that a quality control strategy is developed for at least one accreditation cycle (period between full reassessments) and that this strategy is reviewed annually. The strategy should be developed, taking into account PT and other quality control procedures, but also the level of risk as assessed by the laboratory.

In 2019, EA launched a revision of the advisory document and after a consultation in the EPPO Panel on Diagnostics and Quality Assurance, it was suggested that a plant health case study could be prepared. This suggestion was presented to EA by Valitest WP5 partners in July 2020. EA encouraged WP5 to build a case study for plant health even if it will not be possible to include it in the current revision which is already well advanced.

The case study prepared by WP5 is presented in the Appendix.

This document will be presented to the EPPO Panel on Diagnostics and Quality Assurance in March 2021 and provided to EA to consider the inclusion of this case study in a future revision of the advisory document EA-4/18.

* Definitions of "PM 7/76 (5) Use of EPPO Diagnostic Standards" apply; test : application of a method to a specific pest and a specific matrix

Appendix

Case study – Plant pathology

Accredited testing activities performed by the laboratory in Bacteriology

- Detection of *Clavibacter insidiosus* in seeds by IF
- Detection of *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, IF, real-time PCR, PCR sequencing, pathogenicity test or MALDI-TOF MS
- Detection of *Clavibacter michiganensis* subsp. *michiganensis* in seeds by IF
- Detection of *Clavibacter sepedonicus* in symptomatic plant material by isolation or MALDI-TOF MS
- Detection of *Clavibacter sepedonicus* in tubers by IF or PCR
- Detection of *Erwinia amylovora* in symptomatic or asymptomatic plant material by isolation
- Detection of *Pantoea stewartii* subsp. *stewartii* in seeds by isolation or real-time PCR
- Detection of *Pseudomonas savastanoi* pv. *phaseolicola* in seeds by isolation
- Detection of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae* in symptomatic plant material by isolation
- Detection of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *actinidiae* in asymptomatic plant material by PCR
- Detection of *Ralstonia solanacearum* in symptomatic plant material or tubers by isolation, IF, real-time PCR, PCR, PCR sequencing or pathogenicity test
- Detection of *Ralstonia solanacearum* in water, soil or other substrate by isolation
- Detection of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *vesicatoria*, *X. euvesicatoria*, *X. gardneri*, *X. perforans*, *X. vesicatoria* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, IF or PCR
- Detection of *Xanthomonas fragariae* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, IF or real-time PCR
- Detection of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *phaseoli*, *X. fuscans* subsp. *fuscans* in symptomatic plant material by isolation or PCR
- Detection of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *phaseoli*, *X. fuscans* subsp. *fuscans* in seeds by isolation
- Detection of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *citri* in symptomatic plant material by isolation
- Detection of *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *dieffenbachiae* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, IF or PCR
- Detection of *Xanthomonas arboricola* pv. *pruni* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, IF or real-time PCR
- Detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in symptomatic plant material by isolation, real-time PCR or PCR sequencing
- Detection of *Xylella fastidiosa* in asymptomatic plant material by real-time PCR
- Detection of *Xylophilus ampelinus* in symptomatic plant material by PCR

Considerations for determinations of sub-disciplines

In order to determine its sub-disciplines, the laboratory should list all the measurement techniques it uses within its scope, all the characteristics, which can be individual parameters or groups of equivalent parameters, and all the products, as shown below.

Measurement techniques

Isolation

IF (Immuno Fluorescence)

Real-time PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction)

PCR

PCR sequencing

Pathogenicity test

MALDI-TOF MS (Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization - Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry)

Characteristics

Bacteria

Products

Symptomatic plant material

Asymptomatic plant material

Seeds

Tubers

Water

Soil/substrate

Resulting matrix:

From the list of analyses, the laboratory can then establish a matrix, which will highlight the sub-disciplines, as shown below. If the number of products is limited, they can be included in the matrix. If not, the evaluation of the products can be treated separately.

When considering separately all the bacteria species and combining, for each measurement technique, the different products into one sub-discipline (e.g. one sub discipline combining the analyses on *Clavibacter michiganensis* by IF from plant material and from seeds), the approach allows the identification of 41 sub-disciplines (see table 1).

To reduce the number of sub-disciplines it is necessary to consider all the bacteria species as a single characteristic (table 2).

Measurement technique	SP	AP	Se	T	W	So
Isolation						
IF						
Real-time PCR						
PCR						
PCR sequencing						
Pathogenicity test						
MALDI-TOF MS						

SP: Symptomatic plant material
 AP: Asymptomatic plant material
 Se: Seeds
 T: Tubers
 W: Water
 So: Soil/substrate

Table 2: Matrix of testing activities performed under accreditation, the different bacteria species have been considered as a single characteristic “bacteria”

In the present example, it results in seven sub disciplines (one per measurement technique):

- Detection of bacteria by isolation
- Detection of bacteria by IF
- Detection of bacteria by real-time PCR
- Detection of bacteria by PCR
- Detection of bacteria by PCR sequencing
- Detection of bacteria by pathogenicity test
- Detection of bacteria by MALDI-TOF MS

Proficiency testing strategy

The laboratory should necessarily participate in one proficiency test (PT) by sub-discipline (i.e. one PT per measurement technique: Isolation, IF, real-time PCR...) and by accreditation cycle.

Although the different products have been combined into one sub-discipline for each measurement technique, this does not suggest that they are equivalent in terms of method and laboratory performance. Therefore, the laboratory would be expected to evaluate the necessity to undertake PTs specifically covering all the products in its scope on a periodic basis.

The laboratory would also be expected to participate in PTs covering as many pest species/taxa as possible during each accreditation cycle. To prioritize the participation in the different PTs, the laboratory can take into account the number of testing activities proposed for each measurement technique and product (see table 3), or the number of samples received each year for the different testing activities. Analyses identified as technically challenging or pests representing a higher phytosanitary risk can also be prioritized.

Based on the elements listed above, the laboratory is expected to elaborate a detailed and duly justified proficiency testing strategy. It is recommended that this strategy includes a multi-annual PT participation plan covering an accreditation cycle.

Measurement
technique

Product	SP	AP	Se	T	W	So
Isolation	12	1	3	1	1	1
IF	6	0	2	2	0	0
Real-time PCR	5	1	1	1	0	0
PCR	5	1	0	2	0	0
PCR sequencing	3	0	0	1	0	0
Pathogenicity test	1	0	0	0	0	0
MALDI-TOF MS	2	0	0	0	0	0

SP: Symptomatic plant material
 AP: Asymptomatic plant material
 Se: Seeds
 T: Tubers
 W: Water
 So: Soil/substrate

Table 3: Matrix of testing activities performed under accreditation, the number of testing activities present in the example are indicated for each measurement technique and product. A colour code is used to highlight differences between values.